

FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND SERVICE QUALITY IMPROVEMENT AT ANAN SAIGON

HO TRA GIANG¹ and HUYNH TAN HOI²

¹Hospitality & Tourism Management Faculty, FPT University, Vietnam. Email: GiangHT12@fe.edu.vn

²Faculty of Japanese, FPT University, Vietnam.

Abstract

In recent years, Vietnam's tourism has increasingly developed and received the attention of the whole society. The Vietnam Tourism Development Strategy: "Developing tourism into a spearhead economic sector, tourism accounts for an increasing proportion of GDP, creating a driving force for socio-economic development. Tourism development is in the direction of modern professionalism, focus and focus; focusing on developing in-depth to ensure effective quality, affirm the brand name and competitiveness". Vietnam tourism has been going in the right direction. Therefore, to improve the quality of tourism, and contribute to attracting and satisfying the increasing demands of tourists, businesses in the tourism sector not only need to improve the quality of tourism services but also focus on improving the quality of tourism services. High-quality restaurant services bring visitors a feeling of comfort and relaxation during their vacation, providing comfortable accommodation and the best place to eat at a reasonable price. As a result, the field of restaurant has made great changes and caught up with development trends in the world, which contributes to proving that eating is a very basic human need. As the economy grows, material life is increasingly improved, and people's need to enjoy food becomes a matter of social concern.

Keywords: restaurant, food, business, quality, tourism

A. INTRODUCTION

The restaurant business needs to properly recognize the current situation and challenges of this field after Covid-19, it is necessary to share operating experience, knowledge, tools, new technologies, and new technologies. Forecast market demand trends, and future deployment methods to adapt to new situations. From the fact that Vietnam was awarded the title of "Asia's Leading Culinary Destination" at the 2019 World Travel Awards, the Vietnam National Administration of Tourism has determined that the role of restaurants is the service factor components that contribute to the quality and brand of tourism to promote the destination, attract visitors, generate revenue, build a high-quality source and help improve the competitiveness of Vietnam's tourism. Where there is a special food service, that place has a good impression on visitors, thereby creating trust and helping them satisfy their need to discover culinary arts, prolong their stay, and increase their average spending. Army and generate revenue for the locality (Truong et al., 2017). Therefore, it is extremely necessary to learn about the factors affecting customer satisfaction in general and at Anan Saigon in particular, so that businesses can have more perspectives and understand more about their customers (De Tran et al., 2020).

B. LITERATURE REVIEW

The restaurant business includes the activities of preparing food, selling and serving the consumption needs of food and beverages, and providing other services to satisfy the dining and entertainment needs of customers at the restaurant to make a profit (Berezina et al., 2019). Depending on the type and specific conditions of the Restaurant, there may be different types of products. Food and beverage business activities are very diverse and rich depending on the size of the business. Creating conditions for customers to consume food on the spot and providing conditions for guests to rest and relax (Gustafsson et al., 2006). Based on the food and drinks that the Restaurant serves, the Restaurant is also divided into 03 types which are: The restaurant serves European cuisine, the restaurant serves Asian cuisine and the restaurant serves ethnic specialties. Today, the restaurant business and other types of food establishments have developed rapidly with various forms to serve a wide range of customers (Tuchman & Levine, 1993). For the Hotel, the culinary business at the Restaurant and the dining facilities inside is indispensable. Along with accommodation service, food service has become a basic service for many hotels (Lee, 2018). For some hotels, the development of this type of service not only meets the dining needs of tourists but also creates the brand and strength of that hotel.

C. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Use qualitative research methods to conduct surveys. This is the research method that can reach customers most naturally. Qualitative research is research that answers why and how people behave the way they do (Mukhopadhyay & Gupta, 2014). More specifically, qualitative research provides insights into human behavior. This research explores ideas and formulates theories and hypotheses, and analyzes by synthesizing, categorizing, and interpreting. The study table is presented in text and citation format, small sample size, using open-ended questions, data collection through in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, participation, or literature review. In addition, the combined study Quantitative Research: Surveying 250 customers. Collected data is processed by SPSS and the following methods are used for data analysis: scale reliability analysis (Cronbach's Alpha), exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The focus group discussion method allows members to freely express their views and counter previous opinions. These opinions are made in writing and agreed upon by a majority. The results of this discussion are the basis to confirm the correctness of the model and build official scales to serve the survey. The sample size should be equal to or greater than 100 and the smallest sample should have the desired ratio of 5 observations for each variable. $N > 100$ samples and $n = 5k$ (k is the number of variables). Fidell & Tabachnick (2013) suggest that the sample size for regression analysis is determined: $n \geq 50 + 8m$. To ensure a sample size of 100 increase 40% of the minimum sample size because during data collection will have to remove unsatisfactory questionnaires.

D. RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: The general information of the respondents

Demographic		Quantity	(%)
Gender	Male	100	40
	Female	150	60
Age	From 25 to 35 years old	50	20
	From 35 to 45 years old	200	80
Job	Student	20	8
	Freelance	20	8
	Office staff	50	20
	Business	160	64
Income	<25 million	180	72
	From 25 to 35 million	50	20
	>35 million	20	8
Total		250	100

The statistics display gender is male customers, accounting for 40%, and the rest are female customers, 150 people, accounting for 60%. The age group from 35 to 45 accounts for the most 80%, then the age group from 25 to 35 years old accounts for 20%. Students account for 20 surveys with 8%; followed by freelance accounting for 8%, followed by the group of office staff accounting for 20%, and business accounting for 64%. The results of this survey show that under 25 million witnessed 180 surveys (72%).Next from 25 to 35 million accounts for 20% and the final above 35 million (8%).

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha reliability test results and KMO

Factor	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
TG1	16.69	.645	.663
TG2	16.38	.650	.661
TG3	16.65	.692	.647
TG4	16.60	.658	.658
TG5	16.71	.617	.638
RL1	15.84	.769	.720
RL2	15.50	.789	.715
RL3	15.84	.701	.712
RL4	15.10	.782	.742
RL5	15.75	.779	.718
GT1	16.02	.507	.694
GT2	16.30	.598	.696
GT3	16.10	.503	.665
GT4	16.97	.522	.690
GT5	16.93	.569	.604
RP1	15.40	.657	.735
RP2	15.18	.677	.728
RP3	15.56	.642	.734
RP4	15.42	.659	.728
RP5	15.53	.669	.717
SP1	16.51	.557	.699
SP2	16.54	.543	.606
SP3	16.41	.583	.689
SP4	16.73	.597	.657
SP5	16.46	.541	.605

The results show that the variables have a Cronbach's alpha coefficient greater than 0.6 - less than 0.90 - and a variable correlation coefficient - greater than 0.4 overall. These variables are used in the EFA analysis below. Analyzing EFA factors will show more precisely whether the above scales are separated into new or eliminated factors. From the authors Hoang & Chu (2008): First, the KMO coefficient is 0.50 and the significance level of the Bartlett's test is 0.50. Second, factor loading 0.50, if an observed variable has a loading factor less than 0.50, it is eliminated. Third, the scale is accepted if the total variance extracted is more than 50%. Fourth, the number of factors is determined using the eigenvalue coefficient, which represents the explained spread for each factor, this coefficient must have a value of 1. Fifth, the difference of a load factor of an observed variable among factors is 0.30 until ensuring a discriminant value between factors.

Table 3: KMO and Bartlett's

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.793
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1724.464
	Df	173
	Sig.	.000

Valid scales after analyzing Cronbach's Alpha will be included in the next evaluation by EFA exploratory factor analysis. The criterion of the factor analysis method is that the KMO must be greater than 0.6 Garson, (2003), and the significance level $\text{sig} < 0.05$. The results of the Bartletttest show that with a sig. of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a $\text{KMO} > 0.5$, it meets the requirements for running EFA, proving that the conceptual validity test of the scale is suitable for conducting analysis. Accumulate.

Table 4: Factor loading of independent variables

Factors	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
TG1	.711				
TG2	.778				
TG3	.760				
TG4	.793				
TG5	.762				
RL1		.685			
RL2		.680			
RL3		.672			
RL4		.641			
RL5		.609			
GT1			.864		
GT2			.846		
GT3			.805		
GT4			.898		
GT5			.892		
RP1				.816	
RP2				.805	
RP3				.861	
RP4				.889	
RP5				.879	
SP1					.624
SP2					.636
SP3					.615
SP4					.618
SP5					.602

The factor rotation matrix table shows that the factor loading coefficients of the observed variables all have values > 0.6 . From the above analysis, the scale has high reliability and is

used for regression analysis to measure the impact of independent factors on satisfaction (Lu, 1999). Thus, the scale of factors affecting, the extracted factors are both reliable and valid. The scales are qualified for confirmatory factor analysis.

Table 5: synthesis analysis ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	29.447	6	58.796	142,012	0,000
Residual	26.518	293			
Total	55.965	228			

The results of the model fit test are shown in Table 3 with the Sig value of $0.00 < 0.05$ and the statistic $F = 142.012$, proving that the theoretical model is consistent with reality, and the independent variables are similar has had a linear relationship with the dependent variable and shows that the multiple linear regression model fits the data set and can be used.

E. MARKETING STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE SERVICE QUALITY

Social marketing ideas may be applied to any strategic promotion of tourism and service quality. However, they are most effective when used in high-traffic media such as Facebook, Zalo, and YouTube (Nguyen, 2019). At the point of sale of services to clients, social marketing should be widely utilized. For planners, programs at the point of sale will be more extensively distributed if the operator understands the customer's demands. At the same time, this makes it easier for clients to obtain information from a reputable source. Customers who return to the former site will appreciate customer satisfaction.

Because clients have so many options in today's competitive wood market, maintaining quality standards is one of the most crucial requirements for customer satisfaction. At the same time, communication channels are rapidly expanding, making it simple for customers to forget about low-quality items. This has potentially harmful implications as well as a loss of product reputation. Product if it does not match the above-mentioned consumer needs Service quality, on the other hand, is one of the variables influencing the company's output quality and competitive advantage over competitors. Service quality, pricing, environment, and individual characteristics all have an impact on tourist enjoyment. The amount of information that clients acquire through the online form will benefit numerous ways customers' travel needs.

Many of these studies demonstrate that online marketing, service quality, and logistics may all help to promote tourism (Cheunkamon et al, 2021). Innovators, in especially, have a significant impact on product quality. The study's outcomes are meant to evaluate the influence of innovative practices such as teamwork, internet marketing, customer satisfaction, and supply chain management on performance measurements in the tourist setting (Yilmaz& Bititci, 2006). This research can help provide a thorough theoretical framework for the tourist sector. Furthermore, the results relate to the present base of information by demonstrating the influence of variety, information, and innovation.

Active cooperation, quality of service, digital marketing, and supply chain management should

be actively promoted since these qualities may develop internal customer satisfaction and mutual trust amongst suppliers (Le,2021). Practitioners of tourism based on these findings, creative strategies such as cooperation, service quality, digital marketing, and supply chain management may assist raise individual community knowledge of cultural tourism, improving tourism image, and increasing visitor loyalty.

Travel content firms should use creative strategies such as cooperation, quality of service, digital marketing, and interpersonal supply chain management pellets to foster cross-departmental trust. As a consequence, it should be simple to satisfy clients while also improving cultural understanding and image. These acts can generate new possibilities, increase the possibility of selecting excellent prospects, and contribute to the development or composition of modern cultural tourism context categories, as well as their advantages and additional advantages. The sampling procedure can be utilized in future research, depending on the size or skill of the organization, to ensure a representative sample distribution of respondents from the cultural tourism industry.

F. RECOMMENDATION

The restaurant needs to equip more serving utensils, and tablecloths, replace old, torn, unhygienic as well as aesthetic in eating such as stained white napkins of guest's color, tear, frayed thread, dirty laundry not clean (Dahmer & Kahl, 2008). Liquidation of old items such as forks, spoons, etc., chipped items such as plates, cups, cups, etc. Diners will not have an appetite when using items that are no longer new or have been chipped to enjoy the meal, even this will cause a bad impression to customers about the restaurant's aesthetics and service quality. To ensure safety as well as aesthetics, should replace old food trays with new and cleaner trays. Periodically check the tools to capture the quantity and condition of the tools, thereby reporting and recommending replacement and replenishment if necessary. In addition, specify personal responsibility for managing and using the restaurant's assets. Restaurant managers should focus on designing and expanding the space for the bar department so that employees can comfortably mix drinks at the bar and the bar is open for customers to see. Import more types of wine to meet the increasing enjoyment of customers. Decorate and rearrange the wine cabinet to make it more luxurious and beautiful. Food hygiene and safety are always a top concern of both customers and the restaurant. Good hygiene helps the restaurant operate well and creates trust in customers, making customers feel secure when using the services that the restaurant in particular or the hotel in general provides. Nowadays, when customers come to a restaurant, they not only focus on the deliciousness of the food but also pay attention to the nutritional issues, a balanced variety of foods is the way to solve this problem (Burger et al., 2010). Focusing on a balanced variety of foods is the way to go about this. The focus on a balanced variety of foods, and ensuring adequate nutrition for a meal will make customers feel satisfied, increase the restaurant's prestige as well as affirm its class (Niva, 2007). To welcome and see off guests more thoughtfully, pay attention to the surroundings and focus on the work, when seeing off guests, it is necessary to consult customers about the quality of the food as well as the quality of the service. Does the restaurant make customers feel satisfied or not? The survey of guests helps the restaurant to know what customers are not

satisfied with to correct, as well as continue to promote the points of customer satisfaction. Setting up tables and chairs needs to show more professionalism. The restaurant's tables and chairs are arranged according to the concept like an old market, the tables and chairs will be messy with different types of chairs in no order, and many customers feel uncomfortable because of the confusion. Therefore, the restaurant should reconsider and change the arrangement of chairs to better suit the preferences of all customers. The expression and behavior of the staff will largely determine whether the customer will return to the Restaurant or even the Hotel again. Therefore, the quality and service style of the staff will help the Restaurant as well as the Hotel retain old customers and can attract new customers (Wuest, 1996). The effects will be achieved if the restaurant implements the above-mentioned implementation plans: Helping employees to have accurate service standards and creating synchronization in the service process of all employees in the restaurant. Restaurant. Minimize the possibility of errors during work. Minimizing the possibility of errors in the service process due to language differences shows the professionalism of a restaurant (Harris, 2015).

G. CONCLUSION

Improving business performance is the goal that any restaurant aims for and does everything to achieve this goal. One of the most influential and effective methods to improve a restaurant's business is to improve service quality. Improving the service quality of a business establishment not only contributes to increasing revenue for that establishment but also helps that establishment create a strong foothold, creates a different highlight for the business, and helps in attracting customers to business. Improving the quality of service at any business establishment must fully ensure the impact factors. Only then can the service quality be guaranteed.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

None

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